

Effect of immobilization of N_2 -fixing cyanobacteria on solid matrices and their influence on N_2 -fixing activity and ammonia excretion

S. Suresh Babu and S. Kannaiyan, Department of Agricultural Microbiology, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, Tamil Nadu, India

Immobilization is the process of attaching cells or their constituent biocatalysts to a solid matrix so that they do not move independently when placed in a fluid environment. Immobilization could be carried out by physical means such as adsorption or entrapment in a gel or foam matrix or by chemical methods such as covalent bonding.

In the present study, solid matrices such as polyurethane foam (PUF), sugarcane waste, and paper waste were used for immobilizing N_2 -fixing cyanobacteria *Anabaena variabilis* and *Nostoc muscorum*. PUF was cut into 0.5-cm pieces before use. Sugarcane waste was treated with 0.5% sodium hydroxide to remove the phenols and then thoroughly washed before use.

PUF at 1.5 g, sugarcane waste at 2.0 g, and paper waste at 2.0 g were each placed in six 250-mL volumetric flasks containing 150 mL of N-free BG-11 medium. These were sterilized in an autoclave at 15 lb pressure at 120 °C for 30 min and then cooled to room temperature prior to inoculation of one set with 5 mL of actively growing homogenized cyanobacterial cultures of *A. variabilis*-SAo and another set with *N. muscorum*-DOH. The cultures were incubated under nethouse conditions for 4 wk at 28 ± 1 °C with 3,000 lux light intensity.

Both N_2 -fixing cyanobacterial cultures were also grown under free-living conditions with the same growth conditions as immobilized cyanobacterial cultures. After 4 wk, the culture filtrate from each treatment was collected and the ammonia excreted

Effect of immobilization in different solid matrices on nitrogenase activity of *A. variabilis*-SAo and *N. muscorum*-DOH.

Solid matrix	Nitrogenase activity ^a	
	<i>A. variabilis</i> -SAo	<i>N. muscorum</i> -DOH
Free-living	134	174
Polyurethane foam	247	344
Sugarcane waste	300	428
Paper waste	374	235
SE	7	9
SEd	10	12
CE	20	24

^an moles of ethylene produced h⁻¹ g⁻¹ dry weight biomass.

was estimated at weekly intervals. The solid matrices were used to determine nitrogenase activity via the acetylene reduction assay method.

Anabaena variabilis-SAo and *N. muscorum*-DOH immobilized in solid matrices such as PUF, sugarcane waste, and paper waste have registered significantly higher nitrogenase activity than under free-living conditions. *N. muscorum*-DOH recorded relatively higher nitrogenase activity than *A. variabilis*-SAo in free-living and immobilized conditions except in the paper waste immobilized treatment (see table).

Ammonia excretion was more in sugarcane waste than in PUF and paper waste immobilized and free-living cyanobacterial cultures. Ammonia excretion by both *A. variabilis*-SAo and *N. muscorum*-DOH was maximum on the 14th day and lowest on the 28th day of inoculation (see figure). The higher nitrogenase activity under the immobilized state could be due to the colonization and accumulation of a higher number of algal cells.

The solid matrices also provide favorable conditions for colonization of cyanobacteria on the surface of paper waste and also inside the solid matrices in PUF and sugarcane waste. Interestingly, the colonization of cyanobacteria on the surface could play a vital role in increasing N_2 -fixing activity and ammonia production.

Financial assistance by EEC, Belgium, is gratefully acknowledged. ■

Ammonia excretion (n moles mL⁻¹)

CD ($P = 0.05$) = 8.17

CD ($P = 0.05$) = 6.75

Effect of immobilization in different solid matrices on ammonia excretion by *A. variabilis*-SAo and *N. muscorum*-DOH. PUF = polyurethane foam, SCW = sugarcane waste, PW = paper waste.

Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not ordinarily accepted. Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. Field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.